

User Engagement Strategies in Library Website in University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper determined the user's engagement strategies in library website in university of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to examine users' awareness on digital library website, factors that contribute to users' engagement in web digital library, the impact of digital library website and the challenges that users face during engagement. Quantitative research methodology was adopted for the study using survey research design due to that fact that it is non-experimental research method. The target population for this study comprised of 670 registered users of Ramat library university of Maiduguri, Borno state. 248 sample was used based on Krejcie and Morgans (1970) sample table. The analysis revealed by the majority of the respondents indicated that the users are aware of the library digital website, this infers all that were mention are the factors that contribute to users' engagement with digital library website with the exception of entertainment and online library registration membership and also result revealed that the impact of digital library website engagement by the users was to the very high extent in university of Maiduguri. Recommendation were made, management of the library should create more aware awareness about library website special to the newly admitted students into the system and also the management of the library should make online library registration membership and also make more entertainment on the library website attract more users.

Keywords: Users engagement, Library, Library website, University of Maiduguri.

Introduction

The library website has created a paradigm shift in library. The World Wide Web has made an impact on the functioning of university libraries. In the contemporary age of the Internet which has brought about tremendous change in information technology. The growth and use of online information sources increase its importance and the present generation is very much dependent on electronic journals, e-books and electronic databases. Usability analysis of libraries website

is paramount because libraries' website is taking more attention to serving primary sources of information for their users; and for many services and sources, library users depend on the library websites (Kanmadi, & Kumbhar 2006).

Similarly, Casey & Savastinuk. (2017) opine that library website helps to build a long and strong relationship with the users by promoting library services. To build a credible relationship with the user library image needs to be projected through the library website, it is hard for any library to

establish a credible relationship with the users. To establish strong relationships between the library and users the librarians have to reasonably and cautiously step towards setting up an effective library website so that it could not only help everyone to know about the library at a glance but also feel the effectiveness of web-based services. Present day's library websites act as a main window to access library sources and services. It has become a starting point to access University or scholarly information. Among the many social media platforms currently available in university like face book and twitter among others, the ability to discover user interests can greatly help libraries to engage more users through precise strategic interactions. Libraries have acknowledged the importance of social media technology in the effort to complement the way of libraries in increasing level of user engagement towards library and its services (Awang, 2013).

University of Maiduguri offers a wide range of resources including books, journals and online databases. These resources are essential for supporting research and learning at the university and it's important to promote them effectively to users. By offering social media channels that are always open and participating in conversations with their users, the library is able to constantly evaluate and refine its programs, products, and services and ensure that their users are getting what they need In the context of information searching, user engagement is not only a process of retrieval, but also a process of sense or meaning construction, in which users make sense their current situation with knowledge, ideas, opinions, or effective interactions. Hence, it is necessary to explore the concept user engagement for the better understanding of users' information search process and sense making. This is also essential for the better understanding on the interaction between information users and library web designer.

Statement of the Problem

Ideally digital library website is design is to engage and meet the information need of the library users electronically by keep them up-to-date in their field of specialization and in other aspect. The users are getting engage in digital

library website base on what the library is providing. In a similar vein, digital libraries can potentially create and sustain deep Users engagement with Library website. Previous studies have shown the positive impact of users' engagement with website on harnessing library use and establish a networking with library community. Digital library website was found applicable in engaging to university students especially in libraries. But, the researchers' personal observations show that users are not engaging in library website to the fullest. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the user's engagement in digital library website in university library in Borno State.

Research Objectives

The study addressed the following specific research objectives:

1. Assessment of users' awareness on digital library website in Ramat library University of Maiduguri.
2. To investigate the factors that contribute to users' engagement in web digital library in Ramat library University of Maiduguri.
3. To determine the impact of digital library website in Ramat library University of Maiduguri
4. To investigate the challenges that users face during engagement in Ramat library University of Maiduguri.

Literature Review

The growth and use of online information sources increase its importance and the present generation is very much dependent on electronic journals, e-books and electronic databases. Usability analysis of libraries website is paramount because libraries' website is taking more attention to serving primary sources of information for their users; and for many services and sources, library users depend on the library websites. Pareek and Gupta (2013) studied 52 academic library websites in Rajasthan, and they revealed that the library website is the most significant segment for showcasing its systems and facilities, despite the fact that there are numerous ways to contact them.

They went on to say that the library's website should be more concise, have clearer terminology, and link to other libraries and open access services. The website must be updated at regular intervals by which the user be informed of the happenings of the library. They have concluded that academic library websites in Rajasthan must be improved to meet the growing needs of internet users in the state. Khatri and Baheti (2013) conducted an evaluative study of university websites and their library webpages and found that very few of the university websites provide detailed information about the library and its resources, services. They further suggested that the library website needs to be evaluated periodically using well-established criteria for web design, accessibility, arrangement, etc. Ivory and Hearst (2001) had a survey of usability evaluation methods, analyzed existing techniques, identified different aspects of usability evaluation automation that are likely to be of use in future research, and suggested new ways to expand existing approaches to support usability evaluation better.

Similarly, Verma and Devi (2016) in their study evaluated the web contents of twelve IIM's (Indian Institute of Management) and found out that the websites are attractive to the users since they provide information in a graphical form. Seven IIM's have the facility to view their website in more than one language. Proper navigation tools are also used to link various webpages. They suggested that the IIM's must have their own institutional repositories so the scholarly articles of IIM's could be made available globally. Chow, Bridges and Commander (2014) suggested that the academic libraries' website could be designed and managed from the angle of best practices. They also found that as a part of professionalism librarians only manage the websites. Kanmadi and Kumbhar (2006) in their study concluded that the students are not interested in library websites since they provide inadequate and general information.

Furthermore, Lakshmi and Manivannan (2016) in their study observed that there exists a difference between college websites and library websites with government and self-financing colleges. Self-finance college libraries provide

better facilities to their students in comparison to government colleges. Louise, Dolom and Belen (2018) suggests that the 'About Us' in a website can be used as a platform for promoting and distinguishing the institutions which will provide substantial information for users. Wasan and Chakravaty (2018) in their study suggest, library websites need improvement & library websites should be updated regularly from time to time taking accessibility and other factors into consideration. The librarian should make a proper placement and design a library website where users will get the information quickly and effectively possible.

Haridasan and Uwesh (2013) suggested that the use of graphics and animations on library websites attract users and found helpful to search and browse its content. They also stated that libraries with the help of web 2.0 applications such as RSS and SNS like Facebook twitter etc. can help to promote the website. Konnur and Margam (2010) conducted a study related to five select academic library websites of Bangalore city. In this study, they found that the Indian Institute of Science (IIS) library website is excellent than other academic library websites in selected university library websites. Vasishta (2011) in his study found that university library websites work as the best communication medium to extended information about e-resources. The library website works as a gateway to information and knowledge. It enhances the maximum use of library online services and electronic resources. Aharon (2012) conducted a study to examine academic library websites in the years 2000 and 2010. The result of the study discloses that the content of academic library websites in the years 2000 and 2010 has greatly transformed over the last decade which shows the increasing usage of e-resources and emerging technology with the core aim of facilitating library users. Prakash (2013) in his study, analyzed the content available in Central University Libraries Websites in India some users are not aware of it. It mainly focuses on the information available in the library websites, features of the library websites, online library services, links to other information sources, value-added services and so on

Methodology

Quantitative research methodology was adopted for the study using survey research design due to that fact that it is non-experimental research method. The target population for this study comprised of 670 registered users of Ramat library university of Maiduguri, Borno state. Krejcie and Morgan (1970), who noted that as the population increases, the sample size decreases at

a diminishing rate and remains relatively constant. Therefore 248 sample was used based on Krejcie and Morgans sample table.

**Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings
Response Rate**

From a total of 248 questionnaires administered to the respondent only 203 (81%) copies were duly completed, returned and found valid for the analysis. The results were presented in tables.

Are you aware of digital library website?

Pie chart: above shows the analysis of information on awareness of digital library website in university under study, it was revealed that 35 (17.0%) of the respondents indicated that they are not aware of library digital website while

168 (83%) of the respondents indicated that they are of aware of the library digital website.

The analysis revealed by the majority of the respondents indicated that the users are aware of the library digital website.

Factors that Contribute to Users’ Engagement with Digital Library Website.

S/N	statement	SA	A	SD	D		
1	Search for OPAC	51 (25.1%)	103 (50.7%)	154 (75.9%)	28 (13.8%)	21 (10.3%)	49 (24.1%)
2	Search for Plagiarism checker	64 (31.5%)	79 (38.9%)	143 (70.4%)	23 (11.3%)	37 (18.2%)	60 (39.6%)
3	Dio (ask librarian)	55 (27.1%)	48 (23.6%)	103 (50.7%)	35 (17.2%)	65 (32.0%)	100 (49.3%)

4	Entertainment	34 (16.7%)	57 (28.1%)	91 (44.8%)	41 (20.2%)	71 (35.0%)	112 (55.2%)
5	Providing up-to-date information resources	47 (23.2%)	69 (34.0%)	108 (53.2%)	52 (25.6%)	43 (21.2%)	95 (46.8%)
6	Fast in accessing information	39 (19.2%)	85 (41.9%)	124 (61.1%)	23 (11.3%)	56 (27.6%)	79 (38.9%)
7	Online library registration membership	21 (10.3%)	36 (17.3%)	57 (28.1%)	57 (28.1%)	88 (43.3%)	146 (71.9%)
8	To find general library information	30 (14.8%)	74 (36.5%)	104 (51.2%)	43 (21.2%)	56 (27.6%)	99 (48.8%)
9	To find course material	47 (23.2%)	81 (39.9%)	128 (63.1%)	28 (13.8%)	47 (23.6%)	75 (36.9%)
10	library website is link to social media handles	65 (32.0%)	62 (30.5%)	127 (62.6%)	13 (6.4%)	63 (31.0%)	67 (33.0%)
11	To search in HEC digital library	58 (28.6%)	78 (38.4%)	137 (67.5%)	25 (12.3%)	41 (20.2%)	66 (32.5%)

Key: S.A- Strongly Agree, A- Agree, T.A-Total Agree, S.D- Strongly Disagree, D- Disagree, T.D- Total Disagree and N = Number of respondents.

Table 1 above indicates the analysis of information on the factors that contribute to users' engagement with digital library website under study and it revealed that 154 (75.4%) of the respondents strongly agree that they Search for OPAC while 49 (24.1%) disagreed to that, 143 (70.4%) of the respondents agreed that they search for plagiarism checker while 60 (39.6%) of the respondents disagreed to that fact. 103 (50.7%) agreed that they use Dio (ask librarian) while 100 (49.3%) disagreed. 91 (44.8%) agreed that they use for entertainment while 112 (39.2%) disagreed with that. 108 (53.2%) of the respondents agreed that due to providing up-to-date information resources while 95 (46.2%) of the respondents disagreed to that. 124 (61.1%) of the respondents agreed that they have fast in accessing information while 79 (38.9%) of the respondents disagreed. 57 (28.1%) of the respondents agreed that their online library

registration membership while 146 (71.6%) of the respondents disagreed to that fact. 104 (51.2%) agreed that they use to find general library information while 99 (48.8%) disagreed. 128 (63.1%) agreed that they use for to find course material while 75 (36.9%) disagreed with that. 127 (62.6%) of the respondents agreed that they engage due to library website is link to social media handles while 67 (33.0%) of the respondents disagreed to that. 127 (67.5%) of the respondents strongly agree that they search in HEC digital library while 66 (32.5%) disagreed to that.

This infers that all that were mention are the factors that contribute to users' engagement with digital library website with the exception of entertainment and online library registration membership.

Impact of Digital Library Website on Library Users

The bar chart: above shows the analysis on the impact of digital library website engagement by the users in library under study, it was revealed that 32 (15.8%) of the respondents indicated that the impact of digital library website engagement by the users is to the low extent, 52 (25.6%) of the respondents indicated is to the very low extent, 46 (22.7%) of the respondents indicated that is to the very high extent and 78 (38.4%) of the respondents indicated that the to the very high extent.

The result revealed that the impact of digital library website engagement by the users was to the very high extent in University of Maiduguri.

Challenges that Users Face During Engagement.

S/N	Statement	Frequency (%)
1	Users incapability to use the library website	145 (71.4%)
2	Poor network connectivity	178 (87.7%)
3	Difficulty in accessing some of the web pages.	78 (38.4)
4	Not aware about the library website	56 (27.6%)
5	Lack of free data from the library	197 (97.0%)

Table 2 above indicates the analysis of information on the challenges that users face during engagement under study and it revealed that 145 (71.4%) of the respondents indicated that user's incapable to use the library website, 178 (87.7%) of the respondents indicated that they are poor network connectivity, 78 (38.4) of the respondents indicated that there are difficulty in accessing some of the web pages 56 (27.6%) of the respondents indicated that they not aware about the library website and 197 (97.0%) of the respondents indicated that they lack free data from the library.

The analysis revealed by the majority that the challenges users face is, incapability to use the library website, difficulty in accessing some of the web pages and lack of free data from the library.

Discussion of Findings

1. The analysis revealed by the majority of the respondents indicated that the users are aware of the library digital website this have corroborate with the work of Prakash (2013) in his study, analyzed the content available in Central University Libraries Websites in India some users are not aware of it. It mainly focuses on the information available in the library websites, features of the library websites, online library services, links to other information sources, value-added services and so on
2. This infers all that were mention are the factors that contribute to users' engagement with digital library website with the exception of entertainment and online library registration membership.

This is in line with the work of Vasishta (2011) in his study found that university library websites work as the best communication medium to extended information about e-resources. The library website works as a gateway to information and knowledge. It enhances the maximum use of library online services and electronic resources. Aharon (2012) conducted a study to examine academic library websites in the years 2000 and 2010. The result of the study discloses that the content of academic library websites in the years 2000 and 2010 has greatly transformed over the last decade which shows the increasing usage of e-resources and emerging technology with the core aim of facilitating library users.

3. The result revealed that the impact of digital library website engagement by the users was to the very high extent in university of Maiduguri. In a similar vein, digital libraries can potentially create and sustain deep Users engagement with Library website. Previous studies have shown the positive impact of users' engagement with website on harnessing library use and establish a networking with library community. Digital library website was found applicable in engaging to university students especially in libraries (Mack, Behler, Roberts & Rimland, 2007).
4. The analysis revealed by the majority that the challenges users face is, incapability to use the library website, difficulty in accessing some of the web pages and lack of free data from the

library. Haridasan and Uwesh (2013) opine that the lack of graphics and animations on library websites discourage users to search and browse its content. They also stated that libraries with the help of web 2.0 applications such as RSS and SNS like Facebook twitter etc. can help to promote the website. Wasan and Chakravaty (2018) stressed that library websites need improvement & library websites should be updated regularly from time to time taking accessibility and other factors into consideration for user to have accessibility. The librarian should make a proper placement and design a library website where users will get the information quickly and effectively possible.

Conclusion

University libraries are playing an important role in supporting and disseminating information services through their websites, library websites are the best tool to access all the online resources. The analysis revealed by the majority of the respondents indicated that the users are aware of the library digital website, infers all that were mention are the factors that contribute to users' engagement with digital library website with the exception of entertainment and online library registration membership, the result revealed that the impact of digital library website engagement by the users was to the very high extent and the analysis revealed by the majority that the challenges users face are, incapability to use the library website, difficulty in accessing some of the web pages and lack of free data from the library in university of Maiduguri, Borno state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The management of the library should create more awareness about library website special to the newly admitted students into the system.

2. The management of the library should make online library registration membership and also make more entertainment on the library website attract more users.
3. The management of the library should create more research site on the website so that it will also be of a great impact to the users.
4. The management of the library should draw the attention of use of computer lecturers for proper guide and also assist the users when engage with the library website.

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